

A Survey of Teachers' Challenges of Assessing Domains of Educational Objectives and Bloom's Taxonomy Levels in Social Studies in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was on survey of teachers' challenges of assessing domains of educational objectives and bloom's taxonomy levels in social studies in Benue State. The sample of this study was made up of 162 Social Studies teacher that were drawn from 54 government approved Upper Basic schools and eighteen (18) schools respectively in Zone A, Zone B and Zone C of Benue State, Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design. The instrument used for data collection was Challenges of Assessing Educational Objectives and Bloom's Taxonomy Questionnaire (CAEOBTQ) with the reliability value of 0.82 using Cronbach Alpha. Four research questions and four null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation scores while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test. The study revealed among others that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Social Studies teachers on challenges of assessing the three domain of educational objective ($t=1.41$, $df= 160$, $P>0.05$). There was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Social Studies teachers on challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies ($t=1.51$, $df= 160$, $P>0.05$). It is recommended among others that Ministry of Education should organize special training programmes for Social Studies teachers regularly in order to enhance their skills in assessing the three domains of educational objectives and Bloom taxonomy levels effectively. Teachers should be encouraged to show adequate commitment to implementing assessment practices through provision of incentive.

Keywords: Teachers' challenges, Educational objectives and Bloom's taxonomy levels

Introduction

Education is the systematic training of individual in order to bring about positive change in his or her behaviour so as to become fulfilled citizen. Education is an essential component for development and growth in any society. Assessment is very important factor in education. An educational professional must be able to effectively assess the students' academic development and knowledge of the subjects being taught. According to Knight (2016) assessment of student's learning has often been seen as a tiresome and necessity. Tiresome because of the amount of work it imposes upon learners and teachers. It also encourages cramming, superficiality and conformity and a necessity because without it, students cannot progress to the next level of learning. No wonder, Nwanchukwu and Ogudo (2014) submitted that assessment should be seen as natural and helpful rather than threatening and sometimes

disaffection from learning. The importance of assessment in any level of educational system cannot be overemphasized. Learning is the attainment of new behaviour patterns, or the strengthening or weakening of old behaviour patterns, as the result of practice.

The term learning means changes in our behavior, attitude, knowledge and skills. In other wards we can say that through learning we can feel permanently changes in our self. Learning includes a wide variety of changes in behaviour. The changes may be readily detected in the overt behaviour of the individual or they may be changes in his reserve of ideas. Learning is frequently defined as a change in behaviour which is revealed by people implementing knowledge, skills, or practices derived from education. Basically, Farrant (2013), emphasize that learning is associate with behavioral changes in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains. Cognitive domain deals with how a

student acquires processes and utilizes the knowledge. It is the “thinking” domain. This domain focuses on intellectual skills and is familiar to educators. Bloom’s taxonomy is frequently used to describe the increasing complexity of cognitive skills as students move forward from a beginner to more advance level in their knowledge. Cognitive domain deals with six levels namely; Knowledge (remembering previously learned information, memorize), comprehension (grasping the meaning of information, interpret), application (applying knowledge to actual situation, putting theory into practice), analysis (breaking down objects or ideas into simpler parts and seeing how the parts relate and are organized, interpret elements of structure), synthesis (rearranging component ideas into a new whole, develop creative thinking), and evaluation (make judgments about value of ideas or materials, assess effectiveness).

Affective domain is critical for learning, but is often not specifically addressed. This domain focuses on attitude, motivation, willingness to participate, valuing what is being learned and ultimately incorporating the discipline values into real life. Stages in this domain are not as sequential as the cognitive domain, but have been described as the following: receiving, responding, valuing, organizing, and characterization. Psychomotor domain is concerned with development of muscular skills and coordination. Objectives of this domain emphasize motor skill, manipulation of materials or objects or an act which requires neuromuscular coordination (Bloom, 1956). The complete assessment to maintain standard must cover all the three domains of educational objectives and must be place paramount when the teachers are assessing students’ outcomes. Akinsola (2016) concluded that the implementation of assessment in three domains poses some serious challenges and that most teachers do

focus on cognitive domain without paying attention to other domains such as psychomotor and affective domains.

Studies by Kurebwa and Nyaruwata (2013); Nwachukwu and Ogudo (2014); Anwar and Sohail (2014) Yeke and Ogboji (2018) have revealed that teachers are faced with different barriers of assessing the domains of educational objectives effectively. In the same vein, the researchers observed that the assessment of the domains of educational objectives poses some serious challenges and that most teachers do focus on cognitive domain without paying attention to other domains such as psychomotor and affective domains and even the six Bloom taxonomy levels within the cognitive domain are not usually assessed effectively in Upper basic schools in Benue State. Thus, the study investigated teachers’ challenges of assessing domains of educational objectives and Bloom’s taxonomy levels in upper basic schools in Social Studies in Benue State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Teaching and learning are complementary activities. Teaching describes the action of a teacher that helps students to acquire and retain knowledge, attitude and skills. Learning is associate with behavioural changes in the cognitive, (mental process), affective (attitudes and feelings), and psychomotor (coordinating between brain and muscles) domains. These three domains of educational objectives have always played an important role in assessing the student’s knowledge, attitude and skills. The complete assessment to maintain standard must cover all the three domains of educational objectives and must be place paramount when the teachers are assessing students’ outcomes. The standard of teachers’ assessment practices in three domains of learning in Nigerian secondary schools have reflected the positivistic quantitative

paradigm and have been developed to ensure that students are learning.

However, the researchers observed that one serious defect in the system of assessing the domains of educational objectives is the measurement of students' outcome which is usually directed mainly towards the measure of cognitive behaviour. Yet, even the six Bloom taxonomy levels (knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation) within the cognitive domain are not usually assessed effectively. The researchers also observed that the present assessment practice in Upper Basic schools also neglects the assessment of affective and psychomotor domains of educational objectives.

In taking cognisance of the importance of assessing the domains educational objectives in general and also the Bloom taxonomy levels in particular in Upper Basic Schools. There is need to investigate the challenges teachers incur in carrying out the assessment process. Although, the researchers observed that Social Studies teachers in Upper Basic Schools in Benue State are making efforts in assessing domains of educational objectives. Yet, there are a number of challenges that need to be addressed in order to realize fully the anticipated benefits of these efforts. Thus, the study investigated teachers' challenges of assessing domains of educational objectives and Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies in Benue State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is on survey of teachers' challenges of assessing domains of educational objectives and Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies in Benue State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study:

1. determine the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains (cognitive, affective, and

psychomotor) of educational objective in Social Studies;

2. ascertain the measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains (cognitive, affective, and psychomotor) of educational objective in Social Studies;
3. ascertain the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels (knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation) in Social Studies; and
4. determine the measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels (knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation) in Social Studies.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What are the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies?
2. What are the measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies?
3. What are the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies?
4. What are the measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested:

1. There is no significance difference between the mean rating of male and female Social Studies teachers on

2. challenges of assessing the three domain of educational objective.
3. There is no significance difference between the mean rating of male and female Social Studies teachers on measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies.
4. There is no significance difference between the mean rating of male and female Social Studies teachers on challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies.
5. There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female Social Studies teachers on measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies.

Research Design and Procedure

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. This design was adopted because it is a design in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. The study area was of Benue State, Nigeria. The target population for this study comprises all Social Studies teacher numbering 3,713 from all the 156 approved Upper Basic schools in Benue State. The population consists of 1986 male teachers and 1727 female teachers. The sample of this study was made up of 162 Social Studies teacher that were drawn from 54 government approved Upper Basic schools; eighteen (18) schools respectively in Zone A, Zone B and Zone C of Benue State. A multi-stage sampling technique was used in the study. An instrument known as Challenges of Assessing Educational Objectives and Bloom's Taxonomy Questionnaire (CAEOBTQ) was used to collect data for this study.

CAEOBTQ was constructed by the researcher to determine the opinions of Social Studies Teachers on their challenges of assessing the domains of educational objective and bloom's taxonomy levels. CAEOBTQ contained two sections. Section "A" contained demographic information of the respondents, while section "B" contained a 20-item questionnaire which is intended to help Social Studies teachers express their opinions on challenges of assessing the domains of educational objective and bloom's taxonomy levels. Each of the items is a 4-point Likert-rating scale with 4 response options. The options are Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). CAEOBTQ is a 4-Likert scale with number indicators as 4 (Strongly Agree), 3 (Agree), 2 (Disagree) and 1 (Strongly Disagree)

Challenges of Assessing Educational Objectives and Bloom's Taxonomy Questionnaire (CAEOBTQ) was face validated by presenting them to two experts in Social Studies Education and one expert in measurement and evaluation in the Department of Curriculum and Teaching, Benue State University, Makurdi. The items were scrutinized by these experts. Corrections and suggestions arising from these experts were used to review the CAEOBTQ. CAEOBTQ was trial-tested to establish the reliability coefficient which yielded 0.83 using Cronbach Alpha. CAEOBTQ was used for data collection. CAEOBTQ was administered personally by the researchers. The researchers visited the Social Studies teachers in the Upper Basic schools sampled for the study to administer the questionnaire during school hours. The completed questionnaires from the respondents were collected immediately after answering it. A total of 162 copies of CAEOBTQ distributed to the selected sampled Social Studies teachers and data collected were analysed. Mean and Standard

deviation Scores were used to answer the research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using independent t-test. Independent t-test was chosen because of the categorization of the variables in the study. Again, it helps to find the difference in the means that need to be compared. The filled questionnaires by

Social Studies teacher were sorted by gender, and then the differences in means of both were obtained.

Results

Presentations in this section are based on research questions and null hypotheses

Research Question One

What are the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies? The answer to research question one is presented on Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Rating of Teachers' Challenges of Assessing the Three Domains of Educational Objective in Social Studies

S/N	Item	\bar{x}	Std.Dev.	Remarks
1	Inadequate knowledge of assessment practices is one of the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) of educational objective in Social Studies	3.43	0.87	Positive
2	Limited class time is one of the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.37	0.93	Positive
3	Large class size is one of the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.64	1.21	Positive
4	Inadequate commitment to implement assessment practices is one of the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.78	0.94	Positive
5	The kind of acceptable grading system use in schools is one of the teachers' challenges of assessing the affective and psychomotor domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.77	0.91	Positive
6	Educational qualification is one of the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.73	0.97	Positive
7	Inadequate planning time to design and record assessment is one of the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.71	1.14	Positive
8	Lack of Social Studies laboratory is one of the teachers' challenges of assessing the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.68	0.88	Positive
9.	Inadequate of motivation (incentives) is one of the teachers' challenges of assessing the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.84	1.09	Positive
	Total	32.95	8.94	
	Cluster Mean & Std. Dev.	3.66	0.99	Positive

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 1 reveals the mean scores of the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies in Upper Basic schools in Benue State, Nigeria. The data in table 1 show that, the responses of respondents on all the nine items on teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies were positive, giving a cluster

Research Question Two

What are the measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three

mean responses of 3.66 which is positive (that is, it is above cut-off point of 2.50). This implies that all the mentioned areas are the Social Studies teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) of educational objective in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

domains of educational objective in Social Studies? The answer to research question two is presented on Table 2.

Table 2: Mean Rating of Measures that could address the Teachers' Challenges of Assessing the Three Domains of Educational Objective in Social Studies

S/N	Item	\bar{x}	Std.Dev.	Remarks
1.	Training teachers on how to develop and use valid assessment instruments will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.11	0.97	Positive
2.	Provision of adequate class time or period will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.37	1.09	Positive
3.	Encouraging school administrators to adopt a maximum of 40:1 students-teacher ratio per class as recommended by National Policy on Education will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.54	1.28	Positive
4.	Teachers adequate commitment to implementing assessment practices will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.21	1.19	Positive
5.	Encouraging school administrators and educational policy maker to review the kind grading system use in schools will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.31	1.16	Positive
6.	Enrollment in formal degree programs will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.17	0.99	Positive
7.	Encouraging teachers to create time to design and record assessment will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.42	1.13	Positive

8.	Provision of well equipped Social Studies laboratory will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.47	1.32	Positive
9.	Provision of adequate of motivation (incentives) will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies	3.42	1.21	Positive
Total		30.02	10.34	
Cluster Mean & Std. Dev.		3.34	1.15	Positive

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 2 reveals the mean scores of the measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies in Upper Basic schools in Benue State, Nigeria. The data in table 2 show that, the responses of respondents on all the nine items on measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies were positive, giving a cluster mean responses of 3.34 which is positive (that is, it is above cut-off point of 2.50). This implies that all the mentioned areas are the measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) of educational objective in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Question Three

What are the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies? The answer to research question three is contained on Table 3.

Table 3: Mean Rating of Teachers' Challenges of Assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies

S/N	Item	\bar{x}	Std.Dev.	Remarks
1	Inability to make use of table of specification in constructing test items is one the teachers' challenge of assessing the six levels (knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation) of Bloom's taxonomy in Social Studies	3.29	1.02	Positive
2	Inability to attach adequate weight to each levels during test construction is one the teachers' challenge of assessing the six levels of Bloom's taxonomy in Social Studies	3.31	0.98	Positive
3	Inability to construct test items so as to reflect the construct they are designed to measure is one the teachers' challenge of assessing the six levels of Bloom's taxonomy in Social Studies	3.44	1.18	Positive
4	Inability to consider reliability and validity of instruments before using them is one the teachers' challenge of assessing the six levels of Bloom's taxonomy in Social Studies	3.59	0.90	Positive
5	Lack of competent in computing and using item analysis, item difficulty and discrimination indices is one the teachers' challenge of assessing the six levels of Bloom's taxonomy in Social Studies	3.21	1.04	Positive
Total		16.84	5.12	
Cluster Mean & Std. Dev.		3.37	1.02	Positive

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 3 reveals the mean scores of the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies in Upper Basic schools in Benue State, Nigeria. The data in table 3 show that, the responses of respondents on all the five items on teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies were positive, giving a cluster mean responses of 3.37 which is positive (that is, it is above cut-off point of 2.50). This implies that all the mentioned areas are the Social Studies teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels (knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation) in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Question Four

What are the measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies? The answer to research question three is contained on Table 4.

Table 4: Mean Rating of Measures that could address the Teachers' Challenges of Assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies

S/N	Item	\bar{x}	Std.Dev.	Remarks
1	Training teachers on how to use of table of specification in constructing test items will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the six levels of Bloom's taxonomy in Social Studies	3.89	1.12	Positive
2	Training teachers on how to attach adequate weight to each levels during test construction will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the six levels of Bloom's taxonomy in Social Studies	3.21	0.96	Positive
3	Training teachers on how to construct test items so as to reflect the construct they are designed to measure will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the six levels of Bloom's taxonomy in Social Studies	3.44	1.02	Positive
4	Training teachers on how to consider reliability and validity of instruments before using them will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the six levels of Bloom's taxonomy in Social Studies	3.64	1.11	Positive
5	Training teachers on how to compute and use item analysis, item difficulty and discrimination indices will address the teachers' challenges of assessing the six levels of Bloom's taxonomy in Social Studies	3.41	1.04	Positive
Total		17.59	5.25	
Cluster Mean & Std. Dev.		3.52	1.05	Positive

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 4 reveals the mean scores of the measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies in Upper Basic schools in Benue State, Nigeria. The data in

table 4 show that, the responses of respondents on all the five items on measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies were positive, giving a cluster mean

responses of 3.52 which is positive (that is, it is above cut-off point of 2.50). This implies that all the mentioned areas are the measures that could address the challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels (knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation) in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis One

There is no significance difference between the mean rating of male and female Social Studies teachers on challenges of assessing the three domain of educational objective. The test for hypothesis one is presented on Table 5.

Table 5: t-test of Mean Rating of Male and Female Social Studies Teachers on Challenges of Assessing the Three Domain of Educational Objective

Sex	N	Mean \bar{x}	SD δ	T	df	P-value	Level of significance	Decision
Male	88	3.80	0.13	1.41	160	.161	0.05	NR
Female	74	3.76	0.18					

Source: Field Survey, 2019

NR= Not Rejected

Table 5 presents the summary of t-test analysis of mean rating of male and female social studies teachers on challenges of assessing the three domain of educational objective. The t-test result reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Social Studies teachers on challenges of assessing the three domain of educational objective (t=1.41, df=160, P>0.05). The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that there is no significance difference between the mean rating of male and female Social Studies

teachers on challenges of assessing the three domain of educational objective in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools in Benue State, Nigeria

Hypothesis Two

There is no significance difference between the mean rating of male and female Social Studies teachers on measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social Studies. The test for hypothesis two is presented on Table 6.

Table 6: t-test of Mean Rating of Male and Female Social Studies Teachers on Measures that could address the Challenges of Assessing the Domains of Educational Objective

Sex	N	Mean \bar{x}	SD δ	T	Df	p-value	Level of significance	Decision
Male	88	3.78	0.14	1.50	160	.135	0.05	NR
Female	74	3.74	0.15					

Source: Field Survey, 2019

NR= Not Rejected

Table 6 presents the summary of t-test analysis of mean rating of male and female social studies teachers on measures that could address the challenges of assessing the

domains of educational objective. The t-test result reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Social Studies teachers on

measures that could address the challenges of assessing the domains of educational objective ($t=1.50$, $df= 160$, $P>0.05$). The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that there is no significance difference between the mean rating of male and female Social Studies teachers on measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains of educational objective in Social

Studies in Upper Basic Schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significance difference between the mean rating of male and female Social Studies teachers on challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies. The test for hypothesis three is presented on Table 7.

Table 7: t-test of Mean Rating of Male and Female Social Studies Teachers on Challenges of Assessing the Bloom's Taxonomy Levels

Sex	N	Mean \bar{x}	SD δ	T	df	p-value	Level of significance	Decision
Male	88	3.91	0.17	1.51	160	.179	0.05	NR
Female	74	3.89	0.16					

Source: Field Survey, 2019

NR= Not Rejected

Table 7 presents the summary of t-test analysis of mean rating of male and female Social Studies teachers on challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies. The t-test result reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Social Studies teachers on challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies ($t=1.51$, $df= 160$, $P>0.05$). The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference in the opinion of male

and female Social Studies teachers on challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Four

There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female Social Studies teachers on measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies. The test for hypothesis three is presented on Table 8.

Table 8: t-test of Mean Rating of Male and Female Social Studies Teachers on Measures that that could address the challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels

Sex	N	Mean \bar{x}	SD δ	T	df	p-value	Level of significance	Decision
Male	88	3.99	0.13	1.89	160	.155	0.05	NR
Female	74	3.97	0.14					

Source: Field Survey, 2019

NR= Not Rejected

Table 8 presents the summary of t-test analysis of mean rating of male and female Social Studies teachers on measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing

Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies. The t-test result reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Social Studies

teachers on measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies ($t=1.89$, $df=160$, $P>0.05$). The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference in the opinion of male and female Social Studies teachers on measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study was on survey of teachers' challenges of assessing domains of educational objectives and Bloom's taxonomy levels in social studies in Benue State, Nigeria. The finding revealed that, there is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female Social Studies teachers on challenges of assessing the three domain of educational objective. This implies those both male and female Social Studies teachers' opinions on the challenges of assessing the three domain of educational objective are the same irrespective of gender. It can be concluded that both male and female Social Studies teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) of educational objective in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools are; inability to develop and use valid assessment instruments, limited class time, overcrowded classes, inadequate commitment to implementing assessment practices, the kind of acceptable grading system use in schools, educational qualification, lack of planning time to design and record assessment, lack of Social Studies laboratory, and inadequate of motivation (incentives). This finding agrees with Yeke and Ogboji (2018) who revealed that teachers' knowledge, teachers' qualification and incentive given to teachers has significant effect on assessment of students' affective and psychomotor domains. In the same vein, Nwachukwu and Ogudo

(2014) investigated the standard of teachers' assessment practices in three domains of learning in Nigerian secondary schools. The study revealed that teachers are not assessing the students comprehensively in the three domains of learning rather they resort to the assessment of cognitive domain alone and paying less attention to affective and psychomotor domains.

The finding revealed that, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Social Studies teachers on measures that could address the challenges of assessing the domains (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) of educational objective. This implies that both male and female Social Studies teachers' opinion on measures that could address the challenges of assessing the domains are the same irrespective of gender. It can be concluded that training teachers on how to develop and use valid assessment instruments; provision of adequate class time or period; encouraging school administrators to adopt a maximum of 40:1 students-teacher ratio per class as recommended by National Policy on Education; teachers adequate commitment to implementing assessment practices; encouraging school administrators and educational policy maker to review the kind grading system use in schools; teachers enrollment in formal degree programs; encouraging teachers to create time to design and record assessment; provision of well equipped Social Studies laboratory; and provision of adequate of motivation (incentives) are measures that can address the both male and female Social Studies teachers' challenges of assessing the domains of educational objective in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

The finding revealed that, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Social Studies teachers on challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels (knowledge, comprehension,

application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation) in Social Studies. This implies those both male and female Social Studies teachers' opinions on the challenges of assessing the Bloom's taxonomy levels are the same irrespective of gender. It can be concluded that both male and female Social Studies teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools are; inability to make use of table of specification in constructing test items; inability to attach adequate weight to each levels during test construction; inability to construct test items so as to reflect the construct they are designed to measure; inability to consider reliability and validity of instruments before using them; and lack of competent in computing and using item analysis, item difficulty and discrimination indices. This finding agrees with Anwar and Sohail (2014) who investigated assessing the learning level of students through Bloom's taxonomy in Higher Education in Punjab. The study revealed that inability to make use of table of specification in constructing test items and lack of competent in computing and using item analysis, item difficulty and discrimination indices has significant influence on assessing Bloom's taxonomy in Higher Education in Punjab.

The finding revealed that, reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female Social Studies teachers on measures that could address the teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels (knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation) in Social Studies. This implies that both male and female Social Studies teachers' opinion on measures that could address the challenges of assessing the Bloom's taxonomy levels are the same irrespective of gender. It can be concluded that training teachers on how to use of table of specification in constructing test items; training teachers on how to attach adequate

weight to each levels during test construction; training teachers on how to construct test items so as to reflect the construct they are designed to measure; training teachers on how to consider reliability and validity of instruments before using them; and training teachers on how to compute and use item analysis, item difficulty and discrimination indices are measures that can address the both male and female Social Studies teachers' challenges of assessing the Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study has established that the Social Studies teachers' challenges of assessing the three domains (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) of educational objective in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools are; inability to develop and use valid assessment instruments, limited class time, large class size, inadequate commitment to implementing assessment practices, the kind of acceptable grading system use in schools, educational qualification, lack of planning time to design and record assessment, lack of Social Studies laboratory, and inadequate of motivation (incentives). It was also concluded that teachers' challenges of assessing Bloom's taxonomy levels in Social Studies in Upper Basic Schools are; inability to make use of table of specification in constructing test items; inability to attach adequate weight to each levels during test construction; inability to construct test items so as to reflect the construct they are designed to measure; inability to consider reliability and validity of instruments before using them; and lack of competent in computing and using item analysis, item difficulty and discrimination indices. It is also evident from the findings of this study that no gender disparity exists in the opinions male and female Social Studies teachers in terms of the challenges of assessing the domains of educational objective and Bloom's Taxonomy. In the same vein, no gender disparity exists in the opinions male and female

teachers in terms of the measures that could address the challenges of assessing the domains of educational objective and Bloom's Taxonomy.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

1. Ministry of Education should organize special training programmes for Social Studies teachers regularly in order to enhance their skills in assessing the three domains of educational objectives and Bloom taxonomy levels effectively.
2. School Administrators should make provision for adequate class time or period; and also adopt a maximum of 40:1 students-teacher ratio per class as recommended by National Policy on Education in order to enable social studies teachers assess the three domains of

educational objectives and Bloom taxonomy levels effectively.

3. Social Studies teachers should be encouraged to show adequate commitment to implementing assessment practices (create time to design and record assessment) through provision of incentive.
4. Ministry of Education and school administrators should supply adequate and enough equipment, tools and facilities for effective assessment of the three domains of educational objectives and Bloom taxonomy levels.
5. Adequate funds should be made available by Government for smooth running and management of teachers' enrollment in formal degree programs.

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